

THE FRACTAL ANALYSIS OF INTERPHASE FOR POLYMER COMPOSITES

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INTRODUCTION

The role of interphase layer for polymer composites is well known and the problem about the structure of interphase and about its influence on the properties of composites are widely discussed in literature, meanwhile it has no one definitive solution.

In this work we have used the methods of fractal physics, which are progressing in the materials science last years, in the purpose of more deep and detail understanding of the role of interphase structural component in polymer composites. In this aim we have developed the fractal model of interphase layer in the limits of multifractal model of composite material, according to which the parameters of interphase structure and properties were conditioned by the fractal dimensions of the filler's surface and of the polymer of matrix. It was proposed, that the structure and the properties of polymer were altered while contacting a filler.

THE MODEL AND THE MAIN RESULTS

We have chosen the specimens of composites on the base of polyhydroether and non-treated or treated by the mixture of sulphuric and nitrogenic acids graphite powder.

The empirical correlation of interfacial volume (V_{mc}) from the fractal dimensions of the framework of filler's particles (D_k) and of the surface of non-aggregated particles (d_0) has been obtained:

$$V_{mc} = 0.24 D_k + 0.61 d_0^{-1.7} \quad (1)$$

The analysis of this correlation showed, that the volume of interphase layer in composites is determined by the fractal dimension of the surface of aggregated particles, which depends on the fractal dimension of non-aggregated particles and on the degree of aggregation of the particles. The decreasing of the degree of interfacial adhesion on the boundary filler - polymer increases the volume of interphase layer.

The analysis of the strength of interfacial bond (S_a), depending on a fractal dimension of the surface of aggregated particles of a filler (d_H) showed, that increasing of the degree of aggregation increases d_H and decreases S_a (Fig.1) simultaneously increasing the size of a critical structural defect and decreasing a blow viscosity.

Fig. 1: The influence of fractal dimension of a filler (d_H) to the volume of interphase (V_{mc}) - 1, and to the strength of interfacial bond (S_a) - 2 for the composites with treated (Δ) and non-treated (\circ) fillers.

The proposed approach and developed fractal variant of Griffith equation allowed us to determine the correlation of the critical speed of deformation energy release (G_{mc}) and of the size of the critical structural defect (a_{cr}) in interphase from the volume content of a filler (j_H) (Fig.2).

Fig. 2: The correlation of the critical speed of interphase deformation energy release (G_{mc}) and of the size of the critical structural defect (a_{cr}) in composite from the volume content of a filler (j_H). Points are corresponding to the experimental data, lines - to the calculations.

Thus, the methods of fractal physics for the analysis of interphase may allow us not only to investigate the structure of the material, but also to predict it's structure and properties, while designing composites.